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First Communication Campaign launched

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Communication campaign across DiSSCo national Nodes

Abstract

This document reports on completion of Milestone MS8.2 (Internal Engagement Campaign launch) delivered under Work Package 8 (WP8) which globally covers a wide range of Communication and Stakeholders Engagement - related activities.. The current report explains the context, lists the objectives, describes the event, identifies outcomes and finally defines next steps. As a whole, it gives an overview of how CETAF, as work package and Task 8.1 (DiSSCo National Nodes Engagement) leader, conducted the work towards the completion of the milestone from its conception to its implementation.

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DiSSCo Prepare WP8 – Milestone 8.2: Internal Engagement Campaign Launch

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Task 8.1: DiSSCo National Nodes Internal Engagement

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Abstract

This report serves as means of verification for Milestone 45 (Internal Engagement Campaign launch) from the DiSSCo Prepare Project Work Package 8 (Communication and Stakeholders Engagement). From explaining the context, listing the objectives, describing the event, listing outcomes and finally defining next steps, this report gives an overview of how CETAF, as work package and Task 8.1 (DiSSCo National Nodes Engagement) leader, conducted the milestone from its conception to its implementation.

Key words

DiSSCo; DiSSCo Prepare; Milestone; Internal Engagement; Campaign, Launch, National Nodes;

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1. CONTEXT

Milestone 8.2 (MS8.2) titled “Internal Engagement Campaign Launch” is linked to Task 8.1 (DiSSCo National Nodes Engagement) within Work Package 8 (WP8) which focuses on Communication and Stakeholders Engagement under DiSSCo Prepare project (DPP). WP8 deals with communication and strategic engagement both, internally within the DPP partnership but also, and more importantly, externally, towards third parties. The Deliverable D8.1 “Communication and Engagement Strategy” provided the framework for actions within the work package, including MS8.2, and the guidance to articulate the needed involvement of national participation, through the National Nodes (NNs) that represent all institutions participating in each country, in the development of the DPP project and of the DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) Research Infrastructure (RI) at large.

The WP8 is led by CETAF (Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities) which is a European network of Natural Science Museums, Natural History Museums, Botanical Gardens and Biodiversity Research Centres with their associated biological collections and research expertise. It embraces 37 members representing 63 of the largest taxonomic institutions from 22 European countries.

This entire WP8, but more specifically Task 8.1 which focuses on DiSSCo National Nodes Engagement, integrates the participation of all NNs as direct contributors and supporters to better disseminate and reach out extensively across the RI related actors, from the institutions they represent within the NN to the governmental representatives they need to address. Therefore, a close relationship with NNs is maintained for content provision, update and validation. CETAF decided to hold a more in-depth meeting for the analysis and reviewing of the communication efforts at national level, with the aim to have a strong dissemination campaign that intended to be appealing, effective and impactful. To that end, apart from the NNs representatives, professionals in the communication domain needed to be engaged to better articulate the tools to put in practice, the messages to disseminate and the channels to use.

Due to the constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic on mobility, CETAF organized a virtual working meeting on Thursday 30 September 2020 from 14.00 to 15.00 CET targeting the Communicators identified by each National Node with the aim of strengthening the contact and the idea to relaunch internal engagement with NNs representatives so they can uptake better their own tasks and responsibilities, with a clear focus on external communication of the DiSSCo RI. Both sides of the coin, communication and engagement are interconnected and leverage on each other while these efforts need equally be devoted at two parallel levels, internally and externally.

From the onset of DiSSCo Prepare, as part of the communication and stakeholders engagement, the connection between internal engagement/information and external engagement/communication through the NNs has been at the heart of the strategy and work. At the current phase of the project, engagement at the internal level aims to:

- Foster ownership across NNs by instituting a habit of co-creating and recurrently using communication and advocacy tools;
- Encourage and receive direct feedback from the NNs as the central actors DiSSCo Prepare under the overall framework of the DiSSCo research infrastructure, as well as pivotal advocates within their respective country that will utilize said tools when engaging with external actors.

2. OBJECTIVES

The NNs have been consistently engaged since the early stages of the DPP project and are currently able to resume their advocacy activity which include both virtual and in person meetings with their respective national authorities. Marking the launch of the first internal campaign, this milestone MS8.2 came at a perfect time and sought to expand the national representation beyond the content-related group of representatives to involve the communicators from the members NNs representation.

The internal engagement was built around the communication professionals, in a list provided by the NNs representatives, and constituted a unique opportunity to:

- Present and get feedback from the Communications actors about the external engagement (EE) tools developed so far (brochure, key messages, website);.
- Reinvigorate NNs' commitment by providing them with engaging communication tools;
- Clarify further the objectives of the DPP project and where it fits in the overall DiSSCo initiative;
- Present an idea for an online campaign: *Faces of DiSSCo*. The vision is to humanize the project by showing literally by whom the project is carried, i.e what is referred to as DiSSCo ambassadors.

3. ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGN PROCESS: DiSSCo Happy Hour

a. Description

The idea of organizing a **DiSSCo Happy Hour** arose from the assessment of the need to provide the National Nodes with communication tools to support their advocacy actions towards their national governments, an external engagement tool described in deliverable D8.1 Communication Strategy.

The vision was to hold a working meeting with an “all hands on deck” mentality where DiSSCo communication was elaborated by both the DiSSCo Communication and Engagement team from the DiSSCo Coordination Office (CSO-CE) in close and active collaboration with the communicators identified by the NNs.

Prior to the working meeting, multiple campaign strategies were elaborated while at the end organizing a DiSSCo Happy Hour working meeting was selected with the central piece of obtaining feedback from the nodes. Equipped with a communication-driven perspective and concept, in the months leading to the DiSSCo Happy Hour, the communication and social media toolkits were worked out, which included visual templates, drafts for both an external engagement brochure as well as an internal engagement handbook. Furthermore, social media material was created (Facebook and Twitter covers, hashtags) that could be published on both DiSSCo's social media platforms as well as potentially (and desirably) the member institutions' online platforms.

DiSSCo Happy Hour visuals

b. Tools and mechanism

As mentioned above, a series of tools were generated geared towards both external and internal engagement. As DiSSCo Happy hour focused on external communication actions, the following tools were presented, with the objective of gathering NNs' communicators' feedback on said tools:

- The draft of the external engagement brochure which aimed to promote DiSSCo to external stakeholders from national governments to industry representatives;
- Social media toolkit which included social media platforms visuals; and
- DiSSCo and DiSSCo Prepare templates for presentations.

As a communication tool for DiSSCo Happy Hour, a presentation was developed to allow the audience to visually transfer the key talking points and takeaways from the inaugural working meeting. The slides from said presentation can be found in the annexes section.

c. Invitation and Agenda

On 24 September 2020, the **invitation for participating** in the DiSSCo Happy Hour was sent via email to the twenty-three communicators identified by the NNs representatives as well as representatives of the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office (DiSSCo CSO). The invitation included the purpose of the virtual meetup, reiterated why they had been targeted and selected and the meeting's logistics information.

At this point, it is noteworthy to mention that the communicators identified by the NNs were not professional communicators working in the field as requested but in most cases just NNs deputy representatives, colleagues who had already attended the monthly National Nodes meetings (a recurring internal engagement tool during which DiSSCo updates are shared, and where DiSSCo Prepare Project work package leaders are able to consult NNs and NNs can share updates, feedback on their overall involvement in the project).

The agenda for DiSSCo Happy Hour was as follows:

Item nr	Topic	Lead
1	Welcome	MLK & CC
2	Aims & target audiences of external DiSSCo Communication	MLK
3	YOUR communication and engagement needs	Participants
4	AOB	MLK

Convener: Marie-Laure Kamatali and Céline Cassarino (as part of the DiSSCo CSO- CE, Communication and Engagement team)

d. Participants

A total number of 14 from 9 countries attended the DiSSCo Happy Hour.

The list of attendants with their respective represented country is the following:

Patrick Semal (BE)

Carole Paleco (BE)

Patricia Mergen (BE)

Steffen Kiel (SE)
Maria Marschler (AT)
Jiri Franck (CZ)
Mareike Petersen (DE)
Eva Haeffner (DE)
Niels Raes (NL)
Francois Dusoulier (FR)
Petros Lymberakis (GR)
Martin Vipp (EE)
Laura Tilley (CETAF)
Marine Ejuryan (CETAF)

Screenshot from the meeting.

e. Outcomes

During DiSSCo Happy Hour, the essential components from the communication and engagement strategy were highlighted to set the framework and the drafts of the tools developed to support the nodes' advocacy efforts were also presented.

The participants provided informative feedback that covered the following points:

1. The urgent need for key messages;

2. The persistent challenge in ensuring visibility to DiSSCo through institutional communication platforms and within institutional campaigns;
3. The fact that social media is not the most familiar platform when advocating for DiSSCo was also mentioned.

This feedback was in alignment with the key priorities of the event, and has been considered to inform DiSSCo CSO's current process of developing and updating DiSSCo key messages.

Finally, the attendants also requested to assess the relevance of moving forward with DiSSCo Happy Hour in its current state and take into account key lessons about the first internal engagement targeting NNs' communicators.

f. Lessons learned

As the first internal engagement campaign effort, DiSSCo Happy Hour ended with multiple lessons:

- There is an undeniable challenge in engaging and establishing direct contact with communication departments at institutional level, which is considered an essential target audience;
- As most of the NNs representatives are scientists, they are able to successfully provide content. However, for this specific meetup the target audience were communicators, professionals that work in communications within the respective institution, which was definitely not reached.

Still, the attendance was medium level as half of the nodes representatives participated highlighting the fact that nodes are curious about these communication-related issues and want to work deeper in understanding and defining the DiSSCo communication needs.

In the section below, a plan to address the challenges encountered moving forward is outlined to ensure engagement with institutional communicators when advancing in the use of this type of mechanisms.

4. NEXT STEPS

Following this first edition, a clear need for reassessment of the engagement of communicators is detected. Those actors need to be communicators within the DPP partner institutions, who are key players in the development of the DiSSCo communication and engagement strategy and thus, need to be directly involved in the conceptualization and, more importantly, the deployment of the dissemination efforts.

To identify what could be defined as a blueprint of the vision for communicators engagement, several actions will be carried out during the coming months under WP8:

- Exploring new ways to engage institutional communicators by establishing contacts with accessible near-by institutions (RBINS, Naturalis).
- Scaling the right formula up to all the NNs and thus, setting the basis of a strong network of science DiSSCo-related communicators by being able to show the strong need for communicators engagement.

ANNEXES

Annex A: DiSSCo Happy Hour Presentation slides

COMMUNICATING
DiSSCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections
HAPPY : HOUR

DiSSCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections

Wednesday, 30 September 2020

Agenda

1. Welcome
2. Aims and target audiences of external #DiSSComm
3. #DiSSComm Tools
4. YOUR Communication & Engagement needs?
5. AOB

DiSSCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections

1. Welcome

PURPOSE of the DiSSCo Happy Hour:

- ❑ **CONNECT** IE to EE; recurring moment devoted to external communication actions;
- ❑ **ALIGN** DiSSCo external communication actions;
- ❑ **SHARE** your communication needs, best practices;
- ❑ Collectively **ADDRESS** communication challenges;

DiSSCO
Distributed System of Scientific Collections

2. Aims & target audiences of #DiSSComm

GOALS of the DiSSCo External Communication:

- ❑ **RAISE AWARENESS** around DiSSCo.
- ❑ **ENGAGE** external stakeholders in participating to making DiSSCo a reality.
- ❑ Secure **COMMITMENT** (of national governments to the Funders Forum, of other stakeholders to contribute to the development of DiSSCo).

2. Aims and target audiences of #DiSSComm (1)

TARGET AUDIENCES of the DiSSCo External Communication

- ❑ **INSTITUTIONS** as DiSSCo-members & future users
- ❑ **NATIONAL GOVERNMENTS** as future Funders Forum members
- ❑ **ESFRI & BIODIVERSITY** Landscape

3. #DiSSComm Tools

TOOLKIT for DiSSCo External Communication:

- ❑ Download DiSSCo & [DiSSCo Prepare](#) graphic charters;
- ❑ [Advocacy brochure](#);
- ❑ [Social Media Toolkit](#):
 - ❑ Facebook, Twitter and Youtube.
 - ❑ Alignment strategy
 - ❑ [#FacesofDiSSCo](#) campaign.

3. #FacesofDiSSCo - DiSSCo Ambassadors

*Thank you for attending the
inaugural #DiSSCoHappyHour !*

1. An urgent need for DiSSCo-RI

a. DiSSCo, a pivotal research infrastructure

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) is a new world-class Research Infrastructure (RI) for natural science collections (NSCs). The DiSSCo RI works for the digital unification of all European natural science assets under common curation and access policies and practices. These aim to make the data easily Findable, more Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). As such, DiSSCo enables the transformation of a fragmented landscape of essential natural science collections into an integrated knowledge base that provides interconnected hard evidence of the natural world.

DiSSCo represents the largest ever formal agreement between natural history museums, botanical gardens and collection-holding universities in the world.

b. DiSSCo unites Natural Sciences Collections

At their heart, NSCs are data containers and thus, knowledge carriers. Biodiversity and geodiversity data when pooled together, rendered accessible and managed properly, have the power to inform cross-functional efforts tackling societal and global challenges. As a NSC-based infrastructure DiSSCo enables mapping a sustainable future for the natural world.

Data derived from European NSCs are crucial to understand life on Earth, analyse its history, and predict its future evolution. They act as a driver for implementation of measures to mitigate effects of climate change, halt biodiversity loss and thus procure global wealth to the human being and our societies. Moreover, NSC are foundational to countless innovations worldwide, support breakthrough scientific discovery and support decision-making and legislative processes.

c. DiSSCo in numbers

Currently **121** institutions in **21** European countries are members of DiSSCo.

These institutions host altogether a priceless heritage in Europe **1,5** billion specimens that urgently need to be digitized to provide access to almost 80% of the biodiversity described worldwide. Building DiSSCo will furnish Europe with excellent research through FAIR data, tool up the scientific community with the necessary resources and flag bio and geodiversity as the cross-cutting element to secure our societies living in harmony with nature.

DiSSCo is a data-driven infrastructure, with natural sciences research work at the heart of its endeavour. It is deeply rooted in the determination to support the sustainable use of geo- and biodiversity knowledge as the most powerful mechanism to channel environmental preservation (and thus, to act green) through a profound digital transformation (in doing so to become open and FAIR) of individuals and institutions work.

[DiSSCo in the near future. DiSSCo goals](#)

DiSSCo will transform a fragmented landscape of NSCs into a comprehensive, accurate and sustainable knowledge base of unprecedented scale for bio- and geodiversity data.

DiSSCo will:

- **Be a one-stop e-science shop** for providing discovery, (physical) access, interpretation, analysis of complex linked data, digitization on demand, and support and training services;
- **Optimize collection curation and management practices in individual institutions**, enabling monitoring, specialisation and prioritisation strategies under common research agendas sha;
- **Permanently link a digital specimen to its related attributes** allocated in distributed resources (GBIF, GenBank, MorphoBank, GeoCASE, TraitBank, PLAZI, BHL, etc.), ensuring robust science whose assertions can always be validated or reproduced;
- **Reduce the global carbon footprint with digital access** (by 25,000 annual international trips and 800,000 global shipments of specimens), improve efficiency, make science more responsive to urgent needs, and accelerate biodiversity discovery.

[Building DiSSCo from today .DiSSCo preparatory phase](#)

DiSSCo entered the ESFRI Roadmap back in 2018 thanks to a mature community behind that is gathered around the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities. From that successful step, the Research Infrastructure heads the challenge of becoming operational by 2026. Today, DiSSCo is in its preparatory phase, a foundational and comprehensive step, involving a pan-European effort, broken down in

different EU-funded projects: from designing the blueprint for what DiSSCo RI could be (ICEDIG project) to testing out and understanding the technical requirements involved in making DiSSCo tangible (SYNTHESIS projects), together with the DiSSCo Prepare Project under which DiSSCo aims to pave the path to achieve prime readiness levels in data, technology, scientific dimension, its finances and governance models, and prepare institutions to be able to be active part of DiSSCo as to allow a smooth transition into the Implementation Phase (construction and operation).

In summary, the preparatory phase is thriving to raise DiSSCo RI's overall maturity, which will enhance its ability to successfully take on construction based on clear and actionable guidelines.

How?

- **By improving its overall readiness across five dimensions:**
 - *Scientific readiness* will enable to inform decisions around its future based on the needs of its scientific-driven user base and data providers;
 - *Data readiness* to provide and enrich FAIR data in a consistent, harmonized manner across the distributed facilities;
 - *Technical readiness* will establish sustainable and comprehensive data architecture and technical specifications of its future digital services;
 - *Financial readiness* to develop a robust and comprehensive financial framework supported by accurate and detailed calculations of costs and contributions;
 - *Organisational readiness* will facilitate setting up its overall legal and organisational (governance and management) structures, along with the strategic and operational plan.
- **By delivering a comprehensive Construction Master Plan** to ensure alignment with follow-up projects, minimise inconsistencies and gaps, improve the efficiencies and synergies, reduce costs of implementation, and secure political and financial commitments from national partners.

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#s

[We need #allhandsonDiSSCo](#)

[#DiSSCoready](#)

#DiSSCprepare
#DiSSCprepareEU
#DiSSCollaboration

Annex C: Social media toolkit

- Social Media platforms visuals:

"your DiSSCo quote"

Photo courtesy: David Marcu

DiSSCo #facesofDiSSCo #allhandsonDiSSCo #DiSSCoRI

"your DiSSCo quote"

Photo courtesy: Ricardo Chapin

DiSSCo #facesofDiSSCo #allhandsonDiSSCo #DiSSCoRI

"your DiSSCo quote"

Photo courtesy: Kateri Martins

DiSSCo #facesofDiSSCo #allhandsonDiSSCo #DiSSCoRI

"your DiSSCo quote"

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"your DiSSCo quote"

Photo courtesy: Clint Adler

DiSSCo #facesofDiSSCo #allhandsonDiSSCo #DiSSCoRI

Annex D: DiSSCo and DiSSCo Prepare templates

Outreach tools:

- DiSSCo Prepare Visual charter

Colour values

For print and web

print7web

	C 97	#0F66AB
	M 54	
	Y 00	
	K 00	
	C 65	#7DB8AC
	M 00	
	Y 37	
	K 00	

Stay consistent

Incorrect use of the logo

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Stay consistent

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Stay consistent

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A5 logo placement in headers and footers based on minimal dimensions

Also applicable for slideshows

Stay consistant
In applications

A format posters and leaflets

logo at 200%

Stay consistant
On the web

Graphic Formats
Different formats for different needs

There are different formats of the logo available:
 JPEG, CMYK, high resolution 350 dpi, suitable for print.
 JPEG, RGB, 150 dpi, suitable for web.
 EPS, vector format, suitable for print. (proportional scalable for large solutions)
 For designers working with Adobe applications there is an AI version available in vector format.

- DiSSCo Prepare Logo

[DPP name of the meeting]
WP8- Title

[Date]

Name- Institution
DiSSCo Prepare WP8
Stakeholders engagement &
Communication Strategy

[Reference of the Meeting] / WP8

[Title]

Content

Logo of the Institution

[reference of the Meeting] / WPS

"Bringing the irreplaceable data stored in natural science collections to life and enabling research at an unprecedented scale"

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION !

Logo of the Institution

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Research Programme of the European Union

[reference of the Meeting] / WPS

<https://www.dissco.eu/prepare/>

- DiSSCo Logo.

DiSSCO

Distributed System of Scientific Collections

